

KOMPYUTER TESTLARINING MAQSADLARI, MAZMUNI VA TUZILISHI

Axmedova Zulxumor Ikromovna

Osiyo Xalqaro Universiteti

“Umumtexnik fanlar” kafedrası o’qituvchisi

axmedovazulxumor85@gmail.com

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XXI asr boshidan kompyuterlar ta’limni test qilishda keng qo’llanila boshlandi. Pedagogik innovatsiyalarda alohida yo’nalish - kompyuter testi paydo bo’ldi, unda testlarni taqdim etish, talabalar natijalarini baholash va ularga natijalarni berish shaxsiy kompyuter yordamida amalga oshiriladi. Test yaratish bosqichi texnologik jihatdan turli yo’llar bilan, shu jumladan kompyuterga bo’sh testlarni kiritish orqali davom etishi mumkin. Bugungi kunga kelib, kompyuter sinovlari bo’yicha ko’plab nashrlar mavjud, testlarni yaratish va taqdim etish uchun dasturiy ta’minot va vositalar ishlab chiqilgan. Test nima? Test-berilgan alternativ javoblardan to’g’risini tanlash shaklidagi nazorat topshirig’idir. O’quv fani bo’yicha tuziladigan nazorat testlari, boshqa o’quv topshiriqlariga o’xshab, to’rt xil elementlardan tarkib topadi; mazmun, maqsad, funksiya, metod.

O’zbekiston Respublikasi Vazirlar Mahkamasining 1993-yil, 5-fevraldagi «O’zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy o’quv yurtlari uchun talabalarni test usulida qabul qilish to’g’risida»gi Qarori O’zbekistonda MDH davlatlari ichida birinchi bo’lib testdan foydalanishga keng yo’l ochib berdi. Jahon pedagogikasi va psixologiyasida mustahkam o’rin olgan test usuli mamlakatimiz ta’lim tizimida jadallik bilan tadbiiq qilinmoqda. Respublika Davlat Test markazining faoliyat ko’rsatayotganligi mamlakatimizda testshunoslikning davlat ahamiyatiga ega bo’lgan masala darajasiga ko’tarilganligining yaqqol dalilidir.

Pedagogik testlar AQSH, Niderlandiya, Angliya, Turkiya, Janubiy Koreya, Yaponiya va boshqa ko’pgina mamlakatlarda keng rivoj topdi. Ushbu ro’yxatga asosan turmush darajasi yuqori bo’lgan mamlakatlar kirganligi tasodif emas.

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O’rganish ko’p qirrali jarayon bo’lib, bilimlarni nazorat qilish uning bir tomonidir. Biroq, bu uning ichida kompyuter texnologiyalari imkon qadar ilgarilab ketdilar va ular orasida sinov yetakchi o’rinni egallaydi. Bir qator mamlakatlarda test an’anaviy nazorat shakllari – og’zaki va yozma imtihonlar va suhbatlar o’rnini egalladi.

Ko’rinishidan, ko’plab o’qituvchilar testlarni yaratishda allaqachon o’tishgan va bu juda qiyin ish ekanligini tushunishgan. Tasodifiy ravishda

berilgan savollar va javoblar sinovdan uzoqdir. Ma'lum bo'lishicha, adekvat va samarali test yaratish uchun ko'p mehnat talab etiladi. Bu masalada kompyuter katta yordam berishi mumkin.

Ishonchlik, haqiqiylik, qamrov matritsasi va boshqalar bo'yicha ishlaydigan maxsus test nazariyasi mavjud bo'lib, ular kompyuter testlariga xos bo'lmagan. Biz asosan texnologik jihatlariga e'tibor qaratib, unga chuqurroq kirmaymiz.

Yuqorida ta'kidlanganidek, pedagogik vositalarni yaratish uchun instrumental mualliflik tizimlari hozir keng tarqalgan: o'quv dasturlari, elektron darsliklar, kompyuter testlari. Maktablar va universitetlar o'qituvchilari uchun kompyuter testlari - test qobiqlarini yaratish dasturlarini sotib olish ayniqsa dolzarbdir. Shunga o'xshash ko'plab dasturiy vositalar mavjud va dasturchi-ishlab chiquvchilar mualliflik tizimlari deb ataladigan yangi versiyalarni yaratishga tayyor. Biroq, ushbu dasturiy vositalardan keng foydalanish test topshiriqlarini kompilyatsiya qilish uchun oddiy va ishlatish uchun qulay usullarning yo'qligi bilan cheklanadi, ular yordamida qobiqlarni "to'ldirish" mumkin. Ushbu bo'limda kompyuterlashtirilgan testlarni ishlab chiqishda ba'zi yondashuvlar keltirilgan.

Keyingi taqdimotni soddalashtirish uchun biz bir qator ta'riflar va tushunchalarni kiritamiz.

Ko'rib chiqishni boshlashdan oldin bu mavzu, test atamasining aniq ta'rifini bilish uchun kompyuter terminlarining informatika lug'atiga murojaat qilamiz. Informatika bo'yicha kompyuter terminlari lug'atiga (VD Valedinskiy) ko'ra, test (test) - bu apparat yoki dasturning ishlashini tekshirish, xatolarni aniqlash va bartaraf etish. Test dasturiy ta'minotni ishlab chiqishda muhim qadamdir.

Test - talabning shaxsiy bilim modelining ekspert bilimlari modeliga muvofiqligini baholash jarayoni. Sinovning asosiy maqsadi - bu modellarning nomuvofiqligini aniqlash (bilim darajasini o'lchash emas), ularning nomuvofiqlik darajasini baholash. Sinov berilgan test topshiriqlari to'plamidan iborat maxsus testlar yordamida amalga oshiriladi.

Test topshirig'i - bu mavzu bo'yicha aniq va aniq topshiriq bo'lib, aniq javobni yoki muayyan harakatlar algoritmini amalga oshirishni talab qiladi.

Test - talaba bilimining fan sohasidagi bilimlarning ekspert modeliga muvofiqligini baholash imkonini beruvchi o'zaro bog'liq test topshiriqlari to'plami.

Test maydoni - ekspert bilimlari modelining barcha modullari uchun test topshiriqlari to'plami.

Ekvivalentlik klassi - test topshiriqlari to'plami bo'lib, talabanning ulardan birini bajarishi qolganlarini bajarishni kafolatlaydi.

To'liq test - bu shaxsiyat modeli va ekspert bilimlari modeli o'rtasidagi muvofiqlikni obyektiv baholashni ta'minlaydigan test maydonining kichik to'plami. Samarali test - bu hajm optimallashtirilgan to'liq test.

Eng qiyin vazifa nazorat eksperti - talabanning shaxsiy bilim modeli va ekspert modeli o'rtasidagi muvofiqlik yoki nomuvofiqlik darajasini obyektiv baholash imkonini beruvchi testlarni ishlab chiqildi.

Kompyuterlashtirilgan testlarning (KT) shubhasiz afzalliklari quyidagilardir: tez ishlash; yuqori tezlik va xatosiz ishlov berish; darhol natijalarni olish imkoniyati; barcha fanlar uchun standart test sharoitlarini ta'minlash; test jarayonini aniq nazorat qilish (savollarni o'tkazib yuborishning iloji yo'q, agar kerak bo'lsa, har bir javobning vaqtini belgilash mumkin, bu ayniqsa razvedka testlari uchun muhimdir); psixologni qo'shimcha o'zgaruvchi sifatida chiqarib tashlash imkoniyati (bu ekspertiza o'tkazishda alohida ahamiyatga ega); jarayonning ko'rinishi va qiziqarliligi (o'quv dasturlari uchun ayniqsa muhim bo'lgan rang, tovush, o'yin elementlari yordamida diqqatni qo'llab-quvvatlash); natijalarni oson arxivlash; testlarni bitta yakuniy talqin bilan batareyalarga (dasturiy ta'minot paketlariga) birlashtirish imkoniyati; eksperimentatorning harakatchanligi (barcha asboblarni bitta disketada); ommaviy tadqiqotlar o'tkazish qobiliyati (masalan, Internet orqali).

Kompyuter testlarining kamchiliklari: murakkablik, mehnat zichligi va dasturiy ta'minotni ishlab chiqishning yuqori narxi; qimmat kompyuter uskunalari bo'lgan ehtiyoj; sohada kompyuterlardan foydalanishning murakkabligi; KT bilan ishlash uchun sub'ektni maxsus tayyorlash zarurati; og'zaki bo'lmagan material bilan ishlashda qiyinchiliklar, proyektiv testlarni kompyuter shakliga o'tkazishning alohida qiyinligi; sinovchiga individual yondashishning yo'qligi (suhbat va kuzatishda olingan psixodiagnostik ma'lumotlarning bir qismini yo'qotish); ma'lumotlarni qayta ishlash va talqin qilish bosqichlarining kechikishi (ushbu protseduralarning sifati butunlay dasturiy ta'minotni ishlab chiquvchilarga bog'liq). Ba'zi mavzularda kompyuter bilan o'zaro aloqada bo'lganda, "psixologik to'siq" yoki "ortiqcha ishonch" ta'siri paydo bo'lishi mumkin. Shu sababli, blank testlarining haqiqiyliги, ishonchliligi va reprezentativligi to'g'risidagi ma'lumotlar avtomatik ravishda ularning

kompyuterdagi hamkasblariga uzatilishi mumkin emas, bu esa testlarni yangi standartlashtirish zarurligiga olib keladi.

Umumiy test masalalari va xususan, kompyuter testini o'tkazishning asosiy yondashuvlari Avanesov V.S, Gorbatov D.S., Kline P. Tretyakov P.I., Bashmakov A.I., Bashmakov I.A., Kapustin N.P. asarlarida tasvirlangan. An'anaga ko'ra, test jarayoni juda ko'p tayyorgarlik ishlarini o'z ichiga oladi - testlarga tayyorgarlik (test tuzilmasini aniqlash, test savollari va javoblarini yaratish, test variantlarini yaratish, sinov sinovi va uning asosida test sifatini baholash, blankalarni tayyorlash), test jarayonining o'zi va test natijalarini qayta ishlash. Sinovni qurishning yagona sxemasi quyidagilarni o'z ichiga oladi:

- Maqsadlarni aniqlash (sinov metodologiyasi va nazoratning asosiy yo'nalishlari);
- Loyiha versiyasini tuzish (kompyuter test dasturlarini tanlash va ishlab chiqish);
- Sub'ektlarning vakillik namunasi bo'yicha aprobatsiya va kamchiliklarni tuzatish (tadqiqot ishtirokchilaridan namuna olish);
- O'lchov shkalasini ishlab chiqish va natijalarni sharhlash qoidalari (natijalarni tahlil qilish va hisobot tayyorlash).

Kompyuter testning afzalliklari quyidagilardan iborat:

- Obyektivlik. Imtixon oluvchi tomonidan sub'ektiv yondashuv omili bundan mustasno. Test natijalari kompyuter orqali qayta ishlanadi.
- Yaroqlilik. Oddiy imtihonning "lotereyasi" omili bundan mustasno, unda "omadsiz chipta" yoki muammo olinishi mumkin - ko'p miqdorda test topshiriqlari ma'lum bir fan bo'yicha materialning butun hajmini qamrab oladi, bu esa test topshiruvchiga bilimdagi tasodifiy bo'shliq tufayli o'z dunyoqarashini yanada kengroq ko'rsatish va "qobiliyatsiz" qolmaslik imkonini beradi.
- Oddiylik. Test savollari oddiy imtixon chiptalari va topshiriqlariga qaraganda aniqroq va ixchamdir va batafsil javob yoki asoslashni talab qilmaydi - faqat to'g'ri javobni tanlab, moslikni o'rnatishingiz kerak.
- Demokratiya. Barcha test topshiruvchilari teng sharoitda, test natijalari shaffof.
- Ommaviy xarakter va qisqa muddat. Ko'p sonli test topshiruvchilarni ma'lum vaqt oralig'ida yakuniy nazorat bilan qamrab olish qobiliyati. Shu bilan birga, qolgan vaqtni yangi materialni o'rganish yoki eskilarini birlashtirish uchun foydalaning.

- Ishlab chiqarish qobiliyati. Sinov shaklida imtihon o'tkazish texnologik jihatdan juda rivojlangan, chunki u avtomatik ishlov berishdan foydalanishga imkon beradi.

- O'rganilgan materialning hajmi va uni o'zlashtirish darajasi haqidagi ma'lumotlarning ishonchliligi.

- Ishonchlik. Sinov balli aniq va takrorlanishi mumkin.

- Farqlash qobiliyati. Har xil qiyinchilik darajasidagi vazifalar mavjudligi sababli.

-Treningga individual yondashuvni amalga oshirish. Talabalarning bilimlarini individual tekshirish va o'z-o'zini tekshirish mumkin.

Afzalliklar bilan bir qatorda, kompyuter usullari o'zining kamchiliklariga ega:

1) Insonning kompyuter bilan aloqasi o'ziga xos xususiyatlarga ega va hamma ham kompyuterni sinovdan o'tkazishda birdek xotirjam emas. Misol uchun, agar test jarayoni kechiktirilsa yoki testning mazmuni odamni qiziqtirmasa, ijobiy munosabat aksincha o'zgarishi mumkin: ishning bir xilligi va monotonligi, savollar va topshiriqlarning "ahmoqligi" charchatadi va bezovta qiladi. Ba'zida kompyuter testlariga salbiy munosabat ham teskari aloqa etishmasligidan kelib chiqadi. Sinovdan o'tayotgan shaxs fikr-mulohazalarni olmaganida, xato javoblar ehtimoli ortadi (siz ko'rsatmalarni noto'g'ri tushunishingiz, javoblar uchun kalitlarni chalkashtirib yuborishingiz mumkin va hokazo).

Odamlarning kompyuter testlariga munosabatini aniqlash uchun maxsus tadqiqotlar o'tkazildi. Ma'lum bo'lishicha, ba'zi odamlar psixologik to'siq deb ataladigan ta'sirga ega, ba'zilarida esa haddan tashqari ishonch ta'siri mavjud. Odatda, odam kompyuterdan "qo'rqqan"ligi sababli vazifani bajara olmaydi. Ehtimol, sinovdan o'tuvchining ochilishni istamasligi, haddan tashqari ochiqlik yoki natijalarni ataylab buzishdan qochish istagi bilan bog'liq psixologik himoya mexanizmlarini kiritish.

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